

Review

Exploring Effective Social Media Marketing Strategies

Mokgabo Katlego Loeto^{1*}

¹College of Overseas Education, Department of Management, Nanjing University of Posts and Telecommunications, China.

Abstract: In an era where digital connectivity reigns supreme, the significance of social media marketing strategies cannot be overstated. People use social media to find, learn about, follow, and shop from companies, so if a business is not on social media sites, they are missing out. This research offers a comprehensive examination of effective social media marketing strategies. While many businesses have recognized the potential of these strategies, they grapple with persistent challenges in their implementation. This research aims to bridge this gap, contributing to a deeper understanding of effective social media marketing and offering practical solutions. The paper unfolds with a comprehensive exploration of the background and significance of social media marketing, emphasizing its pivotal role in contemporary business landscapes. Key objectives include identifying the most effective social media marketing strategies, investigating the implementation processes and their impact on business growth, and exploring challenges faced by businesses in this domain.

Keywords: Social media, marketing strategies, business growth, brand awareness.

*Corresponding Author, Email: mokgabokloeto@gmail.com

Accepted: 19 November, 2024; **Published:** 20 November, 2024

How to cite this article: Mokgabo k. Loeto (2024). *Exploring Effective Social Media Marketing Strategies*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(11), 78-91. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14230953>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

In today's fast-paced digital world, social media has become an essential tool for businesses to connect with their target audience. The expansion of internet penetration and convenient information availability on the internet in the last decade has been greatly remarkable and influenced many people in the world. It allows companies to engage with customers, promote their products, and build brand awareness. The influence of the internet on organizations was investigated by a number of researchers who found out that there is an increase in e-commerce activities across various industries (Nakano & Kondo, 2018)

Digital interaction is essential in these times as a marketing strategy because consumers need precise information that is easily accessible. In this view, real estate experts must take advantage of the capabilities of digital marketing to stay relevant. The value of internet in the real estate industry was researched by Rowley, Razali et al. He noted that it was effective promotional strategy (Rowley, 2006; Razali et al., 2010; Razali et al. 2014). The internet offers many opportunities to real estate developers to reach a vast number of people and advertise their business online in order to

preserve time, money and moderate risks associated with real estate transactions. Thus, maintaining an online presence is crucial to the survival of traditional real estate professionals (Yuan et al., 2013).

Social media marketing strategies encompass various activities that leverage popular platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube. These strategies involve creating and sharing compelling content, building online communities, collaborating with influencers, and running targeted advertising campaigns. With billions of active users on these platforms, businesses recognize the immense potential of reaching and engaging their target audience through social media.

Building brand awareness is crucial for any business, and social media platforms offer an excellent opportunity to achieve this goal. By consistently delivering valuable content, businesses can establish a strong brand presence and connect with potential customers. Social media users follow brands to stay informed about their products and services. Hence, a well-executed social media marketing strategy can significantly impact brand visibility and recognition (sproutsocial, 2020).

A study on "Social Media for Business: Marketing, Customer Service and More" by David Cotriss (2023) revealed that social media marketing strategies have a direct influence on sales and revenue generation. By effectively engaging with customers, businesses can drive traffic to their websites, promote special offers, and provide personalized customer support. Cotriss data reveals that a considerable number of social media users conduct product research before making a purchase decision. Furthermore, social media platforms provide advanced targeting options, enabling companies to reach their specific target audience with precision. This level of targeting can translate into increased conversion rates and sales.

While social media marketing offers immense opportunities, on the other hand, mastering social media marketing strategies can be a challenging task for businesses (hubspot, 2022). The dynamic nature of social media platforms requires businesses to stay agile and adapt to changing trends (Alalwan et al., 2017). Consistently producing engaging content and managing online communities can be demanding (hubspot, 2022). Additionally, negative feedback and public relations crises can escalate quickly on social media, necessitating swift and effective responses (Post, J. 2023). Privacy concerns, algorithm changes, and the evolving landscape of social media platforms further add to the complexity of social media marketing strategies (Cotriss, 2022). Addressing these challenges is crucial for businesses to maximize the benefits of their social media efforts.

In conclusion, social media marketing strategies play a vital role in enhancing brand awareness, driving sales, and fostering business growth. This study aims to explore the successful social media marketing strategies employed by Netflix, a leading global streaming service that has masterfully utilized social media marketing to cultivate a dedicated customer base and generate substantial revenue. Their strategy includes creating captivating and shareable content, leveraging user-generated content, and engaging with their followers. By understanding and analysing Netflix's social media marketing strategies, businesses can gain valuable insights into effective practices in brand awareness, sales, and business growth, which can propel their own growth and success. By gaining insights from this study, business owners and managers can refine their own strategies and navigate the challenges associated with social media marketing. Ultimately, businesses can harness the full potential of social media to achieve their marketing objectives and stay competitive in the digital age.

1.1 Problem Statement and Focus

People use social media to find, learn about, follow, and shop from companies, so if a business is not on social media sites, they are missing out. Social Media is a simple yet extremely powerful tool supporting nearly every marketing objective from brand awareness to advocacy over the past few years (Patel, 2022). However, while social media

marketing holds immense potential for companies, this kind of marketing has significant pain points that some businesses face.

A study of effective social media marketing strategies can offer valuable insights and practical recommendations that can be applied to other industries and businesses to propel them to new heights, cultivating loyal brand champions and even generating leads and revenue. This research intends to contribute a deeper knowledge of social media marketing strategies in relation to business growth, sales and consumer awareness.

Definition of Terms:

- **Marketing:** Marketing refers to the activities and processes undertaken by businesses to promote and sell their products or services to customers. It involves identifying customer needs, developing products or services that satisfy those needs, pricing them appropriately, and implementing strategies to communicate and deliver value to target customers (Source: American Marketing Association).
- **Social Media Marketing:** Social media marketing refers to the use of social media platforms to promote products or services, engage with customers, and build brand awareness. It involves creating and sharing content, interacting with users, and utilizing targeted advertising to reach and connect with the target audience (Source: Hootsuite).
- **Marketing Strategy:** A marketing strategy is a comprehensive plan that outlines the goals and actions of a business to achieve its marketing objectives. It involves analyzing the market, identifying target segments, developing positioning strategies, and implementing tactics to effectively reach and engage customers (Source: Kotler and Keller, "Marketing Management").
- **Influencer Marketing:** Influencer marketing is a type of marketing strategy that involves collaborating with influential individuals on social media to promote products or services. These individuals, known as influencers, have a dedicated following and the ability to impact the purchasing decisions of their audience (Source: Forbes).
- **Business Growth:** Business growth refers to the increase in a company's revenue, market share, and profitability over time. It can be achieved through various strategies such as expanding into new markets, launching new products, acquiring competitors, or increasing customer retention (Source: Entrepreneur).
- **Brand Awareness:** Brand awareness is the level of recognition and familiarity that a brand has among its target audience. It measures how well customers can identify and recall a particular brand and its associations when prompted (Source: Aaker, "Building Strong Brands").
- **Social Media Marketing Strategy:** A social media marketing strategy is a plan that outlines how a business will use social media platforms to achieve its marketing objectives. It includes defining target audience, selecting appropriate platforms, creating content, engaging with users, and measuring performance (Source: Chaffey and Smith, "Digital Marketing Excellence").
- **Business Plan:** A business plan is a formal document that outlines the goals, strategies, and financial projections of a business. It serves as a roadmap for entrepreneurs and managers, providing a comprehensive overview of the business, its target market, competition, and operational plans (Source: Small Business Administration).

Marketing Theories

Marketing theories provide frameworks and models that guide businesses in understanding consumer behaviour, market dynamics, and strategic decision-making. Several prominent marketing theories have emerged over the years, such as the Marketing Mix (4Ps) by McCarthy, which emphasizes the elements of product, price, place, and promotion as critical components of a marketing strategy. The Value Chain theory by Porter focuses on the analysis of a company's internal operations and value creation activities. The Diffusion of Innovation theory by Rogers explores how new

products or ideas spread among consumers. These theories and others offer valuable insights into various aspects of marketing strategy formulation and implementation.

1. Marketing Mix (4Ps):

The Marketing Mix, also known as the 4Ps, is a foundational marketing theory developed by Jerome McCarthy. It comprises four elements: product, price, place, and promotion. However, the marketing mix now increasingly includes other P's like packaging, positioning, people, and even politics as vital mix elements. The product element refers to the goods or services a company offers to meet customer needs. Price encompasses the strategies and considerations related to setting a competitive price for the product. Place focuses on distribution channels and ensuring the product is available to customers in the right locations. Promotion involves the various activities used to communicate the value of the product and persuade customers to make a purchase. The Marketing Mix theory emphasizes the need to balance these four elements effectively to create a successful marketing strategy.

Marketing mix- 4P's

Fig. 1: Marketing Mix-4P's

Fig. 1 showcases the interdependency and balance between these elements in a company's marketing strategy. Each circle can further be expanded to include specific tactics, such as product features, pricing strategies, distribution channels, and promotional activities.

2. Value Chain by Porter:

In his book *Competitive Advantage* from 1985, Michael Porter introduced the concept of the Porter's value chain for corporate management. It provides a framework for primary and support activities within a company's operations to produce value for its clients. In result, this tactic boosts competitive advantage and increases profitability.

It identifies. Primary activities include inbound logistics (sourcing and receiving materials), operations (transforming inputs into outputs), outbound logistics (storage and distribution of finished products), marketing and sales, and customer service. Support activities include procurement, technology development, human resource management, and firm infrastructure. By identifying these activities and optimizing their efficiency, a company can gain a competitive advantage and create value for customers.

Fig. 2: Value Chain Analysis

The Value Chain can be illustrated as a series of connected boxes or steps, depicting the primary and support activities of a company. Each box represents an activity, such as inbound logistics, operations, marketing and sales, and customer service. The illustration shows how these activities are interconnected and contribute to the overall value creation process within the company.

3. Diffusion of Innovation:

It stands to reason that not everyone will purchase a new item at the same time. Before a product is generally released, some people will strive to get an early version or hurry out and buy it first. Others will hold off on making a purchase until a product has gained widespread acceptance. Everett Rogers identified this phenomenon in 1962 and labelled it as the "diffusion of innovation." He created a theory to back it up, describing how, why, and how quickly members of a social system may accept new ideas. The hypothesis categorizes consumers into several categories that share particular characteristics.

Fig. 3: Diffusion of Innovation

The theory identifies five categories of adopters: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. Innovators are the first to embrace a new innovation, while laggards are the last to adopt. The theory highlights factors influencing the adoption process, such as the perceived benefits, ease of use, compatibility with existing behaviors, and the influence of social networks. Understanding the diffusion process is crucial for marketers to effectively introduce and promote new products or innovations in the market.

The Process for Diffusion of Innovation and Social Media Marketing

Scholars have been intrigued by investigating the reasons and purpose of internet users' activities since the invention of mass media (Katz et al., 1973). The phenomenon described in the uses and gratification theory (U&G) was initially intended to emphasize a better understanding of the individual or collective psychological factors that contribute to media consumption and gratification (McQuail, 1984). This allows scholars and media practitioners to create effective methods for improving media functionality in order to achieve their intended goals (Blumler, 2019). Other studies have looked at what influences how businesses use social media (Ćirić et al., 2018), what drives people to use social media (Tao et al., 2020), and why people use social media to share information (Lee and Suzuki, 2020).

According to Vannucci and McCauley Ohannessian, 2019, and general findings and discussions on social media marketing, the Diffusion of Innovation theory can be implemented in the context of social media marketing by understanding the five-stage process for the decision diffusion of innovation and applying it to the adoption of social media platforms or strategies. Here's how each stage can be related to social media marketing:

Fig. 4: Communication Channels

1. **Knowledge:** In this stage, potential adopters become aware of the innovation, in this case, social media marketing. Marketers can create awareness by providing educational content, case studies, and success stories that highlight the benefits and potential of social media marketing. This can be done through blog posts, webinars, or industry events.
2. **Persuasion:** In the persuasion stage, marketers aim to convince potential adopters of the value and advantages of social media marketing. This can be achieved through targeted messaging, testimonials, and demonstrating the success of businesses that have implemented social media strategies. Social media platforms themselves can play a crucial role in this stage by showcasing success stories and providing data-driven insights on the effectiveness of their advertising and engagement tools.
3. **Decision:** The decision stage involves potential adopters evaluating the benefits and drawbacks of adopting social media marketing. Marketers can facilitate the decision-making process by providing detailed information, cost-benefit analyses, and comparisons to traditional marketing methods. Offering consultations or free trials can help potential adopters experience the benefits firsthand and make an informed decision.
4. **Implementation:** Once the decision to adopt social media marketing is made, marketers need to assist businesses in implementing their strategies effectively. This may involve providing training, resources, and support to ensure that businesses can leverage social media platforms optimally. Sharing best practices, case studies, and offering ongoing guidance can help businesses overcome implementation challenges.
5. **Confirmation:** The confirmation stage involves the adopter's evaluation of the outcomes and benefits derived from using social media marketing. Marketers can facilitate this stage by measuring and sharing key performance indicators (KPIs), such as engagement rates, website traffic, lead generation, and sales conversions.

This feedback loop reinforces the effectiveness of social media marketing and encourages ongoing adoption and innovation.

By understanding the five-stage process of the Diffusion of Innovation theory and applying it to social media marketing, businesses can develop targeted strategies to educate, persuade, and support the adoption of social media platforms and tactics (Tao et al., 2020). It helps businesses navigate the challenges associated with adopting new marketing techniques and enhances their chances of successful implementation and long-term growth (Ćirić et al., 2018).

Marketing Strategies

1. **Digital Marketing Strategies:** Numerous studies have focused on digital marketing strategies and their impact on businesses. For instance, Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) conducted a study on the effectiveness of online advertising, search engine optimization (SEO), email marketing, and social media marketing. They found that a well-integrated digital marketing strategy, combining these elements, can lead to increased brand awareness, customer engagement, and conversion rates. Furthermore, studies by Liang and Turban (2011) and Barker et al. (2017) emphasized the significance of personalized content, customer relationship management (CRM), and data-driven marketing in achieving marketing success in the digital age.
2. **Branding and Positioning Strategies:** Research on branding and positioning strategies has provided insights into how businesses can differentiate themselves and create a strong brand identity. A study by Keller (2013) highlighted the importance of brand positioning, brand image, and brand equity in influencing customer perceptions and preferences. It demonstrated that effective branding strategies, such as brand storytelling and emotional appeals, can enhance brand loyalty and customer engagement. Additionally, research by Aaker (2014) focused on brand personality and how it influences consumer behavior and purchase decisions.
3. **Product and Pricing Strategies:** Product and pricing strategies play a critical role in marketing success. Various studies have examined the impact of product innovation, product quality, and pricing strategies on business performance. A research by Christensen (2013) emphasized the significance of disruptive innovation and the need for businesses to constantly adapt and innovate to stay competitive. Furthermore, studies by Nagle and Hogan (2016) discussed pricing strategies, including value-based pricing and dynamic pricing, and their effects on customer perceptions, willingness to pay, and overall profitability.
4. **Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) Strategies:** Integrated marketing communication strategies focus on creating a consistent and unified brand message across various marketing channels. Research has shown that effective IMC strategies positively impact brand awareness, customer engagement, and purchase intentions. For instance, studies by Schultz et al. (2019) and Fill and Turnbull (2019) emphasized the importance of aligning marketing messages, utilizing multiple communication channels, and leveraging digital platforms to deliver a cohesive brand experience.

Process of Marketing Strategy

Research on the process of marketing has shed light on various components and stages involved in successful marketing campaigns.

1. **Market Analysis and Research:** Empirical research has emphasized the importance of conducting thorough market analysis and research as the foundation of effective marketing strategies. Studies by Raju et al. (2008) and Kotler and Keller (2016) highlighted the significance of gathering data and insights about customer needs, competitor analysis, and market trends. Research in this area has also explored the role of market segmentation, targeting, and positioning in developing targeted and relevant marketing strategies.
2. **Strategy Formulation:** Empirical studies have investigated the process of strategy formulation in marketing. Research by Mintzberg (1994) and Porter (1996) examined various strategic frameworks, such as SWOT analysis, Porter's Five Forces, and the Value Chain, which help businesses identify their competitive advantage and

develop effective marketing strategies. Additionally, empirical studies have explored the role of innovation, differentiation, and value proposition in strategy formulation.

3. **Implementation and Execution:** The implementation and execution of marketing strategies are critical for achieving desired outcomes. Empirical research has examined the factors that influence successful strategy implementation. Studies by Katsikeas et al. (2016) and Verhoef et al. (2017) highlighted the importance of organizational alignment, resource allocation, and the involvement of key stakeholders in executing marketing strategies. Moreover, empirical studies have explored the role of marketing capabilities, such as marketing planning, marketing organization, and marketing control systems, in driving effective strategy implementation.
4. **Evaluation and Control:** The evaluation and control of marketing strategies are essential for monitoring performance and making necessary adjustments. Empirical research has explored various metrics and measurement approaches to assess the effectiveness of marketing strategies. Studies by West et al. (2010) and Wijaya and Henley (2019) highlighted the importance of setting clear objectives, tracking key performance indicators (KPIs), and utilizing marketing analytics to evaluate strategy performance. Furthermore, research has examined the role of feedback mechanisms and continuous learning in improving marketing strategies over time.

Social Media Marketing Strategies

Social media marketing (SMM) (also known as digital marketing and e-marketing) is the use of social media—the platforms on which users build social networks and share information—to build a company's brand, increase sales, and drive website traffic. (Hayes).

1. ***Effectiveness of Social Media Marketing:*** Numerous empirical studies have examined the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies in achieving various marketing objectives. For instance, research by Mangold and Faulds (2009) found a positive correlation between social media engagement and brand loyalty. Similarly, studies by Liang and Turban (2011) and Wu et al. (2011) demonstrated that social media marketing positively impacts brand awareness, customer engagement, and purchase intention. These findings highlight the potential of social media as a powerful marketing tool for businesses.
2. ***Influence of Social Media on Consumer Behavior:*** Empirical research has also explored the influence of social media on consumer behavior. Studies by Cheung et al. (2011) and Chang et al. (2015) revealed that social media recommendations and user-generated content significantly affect consumers' purchase decisions. Moreover, research by Kim and Ko (2012) demonstrated that social media interactions and information-sharing play a vital role in shaping consumers' perceptions and attitudes towards brands. Understanding the impact of social media on consumer behavior is crucial for businesses to develop effective marketing strategies.
3. ***Best Practices in Social Media Marketing:*** Empirical studies have identified best practices and strategies that businesses can adopt to maximize the effectiveness of their social media marketing efforts. For example, research by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) highlighted the importance of engaging and interactive content, timely responses to customer queries, and building relationships with online communities. Additionally, studies by Kietzmann et al. (2011) and Boyd et al. (2013) emphasized the significance of utilizing multiple social media platforms, targeting specific audience segments, and leveraging influencer marketing for greater impact.
4. ***Challenges and Limitations of Social Media Marketing:*** While social media marketing offers immense opportunities, it also presents challenges for businesses. Empirical research has explored these challenges, such as information overload, privacy concerns, and negative user-generated content. Studies by Wirtz and Lwin (2009) and Stephen and Galak (2012) shed light on the potential risks and limitations associated with social media marketing. Understanding these challenges can help businesses develop strategies to mitigate risks and maximize the benefits of social media marketing.

Research Gap

This literature review highlights key research gaps in the field of social media marketing strategies. The following areas have received limited attention and require further investigation:

1. **Effectiveness of Influencer Marketing:** There is a need for empirical studies to examine the effectiveness of influencer marketing campaigns in terms of brand awareness, customer engagement, and purchase behavior.
2. **Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Social Media Marketing:** Limited research has explored the use of AI algorithms and automated content creation in social media marketing. Future studies can investigate the benefits, challenges, and ethical implications of AI integration in social media marketing.
3. **Cross-Cultural Differences in Social Media Marketing:** Understanding how cultural factors influence social media usage and the effectiveness of marketing strategies across different cultures requires further empirical exploration.
4. **Long-Term Effects of Social Media Marketing:** Limited research has examined the sustained impact of social media marketing on brand loyalty, customer retention, and business growth over an extended period.
5. **Measurement and Evaluation of Social Media Marketing Effectiveness:** Standardized measurement approaches and comprehensive evaluation models are needed to effectively measure and evaluate the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies.

Addressing these research gaps will contribute to a deeper understanding of social media marketing strategies and provide valuable insights for businesses to enhance their social media marketing efforts. Further research in these areas will help bridge the existing knowledge gap and advance the field of social media marketing.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for understanding social media marketing strategies involves key components and concepts that contribute to the effective utilization of social media platforms for marketing purposes. This framework provides a theoretical lens through which businesses can analyze, plan, and implement their social media marketing strategies. The following elements are integral to this conceptual framework:

1. **Social Media Platforms:** This component encompasses the various social media platforms available, such as TikTok, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, and others. Each platform has unique features, audience demographics, and engagement dynamics. Understanding the characteristics and functionalities of different platforms helps businesses select the most appropriate ones based on their target audience and marketing objectives.
2. **Target Audience:** Identifying the target audience is essential in social media marketing. Businesses need to understand their customers' demographics, psychographics, preferences, and behaviors to tailor their social media content and engagement strategies effectively. This involves conducting market research, analyzing consumer data, and segmenting the target audience to create personalized and relevant content.
3. **Content Strategy:** Developing a robust content strategy is crucial for social media marketing success. This component involves creating engaging and shareable content that aligns with the target audience's interests, needs, and preferences. Content can take various forms, such as text, images, videos, infographics, and user-generated content. A well-defined content strategy ensures consistency, brand messaging, and value proposition across social media platforms.
4. **Engagement and Community Building:** Engagement plays a vital role in social media marketing. This component focuses on fostering interactions, conversations, and relationships with the target audience. It involves actively responding to comments and messages, encouraging user-generated content, and leveraging social media features such as polls, contests, and live videos to encourage participation. Community building

involves cultivating a loyal and active following, nurturing brand advocates, and creating a sense of belonging among followers.

5. **Metrics and Analytics:** Metrics and analytics are essential for measuring the effectiveness and impact of social media marketing strategies. This component involves setting specific goals and key performance indicators (KPIs) to track and evaluate the success of campaigns. Metrics can include reach, engagement rate, conversion rate, website traffic, and sales attributed to social media efforts. Analyzing these metrics helps businesses refine their strategies, optimize performance, and demonstrate the ROI of their social media marketing initiatives.
6. **Integration with Overall Marketing Strategy:** Social media marketing should be integrated into the broader marketing strategy of a business. This component emphasizes aligning social media efforts with overall marketing objectives, branding guidelines, and customer experience initiatives. Integration ensures consistency, synergy, and a unified approach across all marketing channels and touchpoints.

By considering these key components within the conceptual framework, businesses can develop effective social media marketing strategies that drive brand awareness, customer engagement, and ultimately contribute to business growth. It provides a structured approach for understanding and leveraging the power of social media platforms in achieving marketing objectives.

2.8 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for understanding social media marketing strategies incorporates theoretical concepts and models that guide the understanding and implementation of social media marketing efforts. It provides a theoretical lens through which businesses can analyze, plan, and execute their social media strategies. The following elements are integral to this theoretical framework:

1. **Social Influence Theory:** Social influence theory suggests that individuals' behaviors, attitudes, and decisions are influenced by their social environment. This theory emphasizes the power of social interactions and networks in shaping consumer behavior. In the context of social media marketing, businesses can leverage social influence theory by identifying and engaging with key influencers, cultivating brand advocates, and encouraging social sharing and peer recommendations.
2. **Communication Theory:** Communication theory examines how messages are transmitted, received, and interpreted by individuals and groups. It emphasizes the importance of effective communication in achieving desired outcomes. In social media marketing, communication theory helps businesses craft compelling messages, engage in two-way communication with their audience, and utilize persuasive techniques to convey their brand value and foster engagement.
3. **Relationship Marketing:** Relationship marketing focuses on building long-term and mutually beneficial relationships with customers. It emphasizes the importance of customer retention, loyalty, and satisfaction. In the context of social media marketing, relationship marketing theories guide businesses in nurturing customer relationships through personalized interactions, timely responses, and tailored content. This fosters brand loyalty, advocacy, and positive word-of-mouth.
4. **Customer Engagement:** Customer engagement theory centers on creating meaningful and interactive experiences that capture customers' attention and drive their involvement. It emphasizes the importance of actively engaging customers to foster brand connection and loyalty. In social media marketing, businesses can employ customer engagement strategies such as gamification, user-generated content campaigns, and interactive contests to encourage participation, deepen customer relationships, and enhance brand experiences.
5. **Innovation Diffusion Theory:** Innovation diffusion theory explores how new ideas, products, or technologies are adopted and spread within a population. It identifies key factors that influence the adoption process, including the characteristics of the innovation, communication channels, social influence, and adopter

categories. In the context of social media marketing, innovation diffusion theory helps businesses understand how social media platforms and strategies are adopted and accepted by different customer segments. It informs decisions on targeting early adopters, leveraging influencers, and crafting persuasive messaging to drive adoption and diffusion of social media marketing practices.

By integrating these theoretical concepts into the framework, businesses can gain a deeper understanding of the underlying principles and dynamics that drive successful social media marketing strategies. This theoretical framework guides businesses in developing effective communication strategies, fostering customer relationships, driving customer engagement, and leveraging social influence to achieve their marketing objectives in the realm of social media.

Conclusion

In conclusion, effectively highlighted the significance of social media marketing strategies for businesses. It has discussed various aspects of marketing strategies, including digital marketing, branding, product and pricing strategies, and integrated marketing communication. Businesses can learn from different approaches, which focus on personalized content, targeted advertising, interactive customer engagement, and the use of influencers. By adopting such customer-centric strategies and leveraging social media platforms, businesses can enhance brand awareness, foster customer engagement, and drive business growth.

This study serves as a valuable resource for businesses to understand the current landscape of social media marketing strategies and identify areas for improvement. It encourages businesses to stay agile, adapt to changing trends, and embrace innovation to effectively leverage social media for marketing success. By continuously learning from successful examples and implementing effective strategies, businesses can maximize their social media presence and achieve their marketing objectives in today's digital era.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: To my mother, Phetogo Loeto, thank you for your unwavering support, understanding, and encouragement, your belief in me has been a constant source of strength and motivation. I love you.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Alves, Helena, et al. "Social Media Marketing: A Literature Review and Implications." *Psychology & Marketing*, vol. 33, no. 12, 11 Nov. 2016, pp. 1029–1038, onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/mar.20936, 10.1002/mar.20936.
2. Amy Van Looy. *Social Media Management*. Cham Springer International Publishing Imprint: Springer, 2016.
3. Anggraeni, F.D. "Marketing Paper Netflix." Pdfcoffee.com, pdfcoffee.com/marketing-paper-netflix-pdf-free.html. Accessed 7 Dec. 2022.
4. Arun, R. "A Case Study on Netflix Marketing Strategy | Simplilearn." *Simplilearn.com*, 15 July 2022, www.simplilearn.com/tutorials/marketing-case-studies-tutorial/netflix-marketing-strategy#:~:text=and%20website%20optimization.-.

5. Awad, Ala Shakeeb, et al. "Mode of Collaboration between the Pharmaceutical Firms and Pharmacists: An Empirical Investigation of Social Media Marketing Activities." *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 20, 21 Oct. 2022, p. 13624, 10.3390/su142013624. Accessed 15 Nov. 2022.
6. Baldwin, Courtney S. "The Impact of Web-Based Technology on Small Businesses." *Business and Management Studies*, vol. 1, no. 1, 13 Feb. 2015, 10.11114/bms.v1i1.681. Accessed 4 Dec. 2019.
7. Banerjee, Probir, et al. "Role of Trialability in B2B E-Business Adoption: Theoretical Insights from Two Case Studies." *Behaviour & Information Technology*, vol. 31, no. 9, Sept. 2012, pp. 815–827, 10.1080/0144929x.2010.497564. Accessed 8 Aug. 2019.
8. Bhargava, V. "How Netflix Uses Social Listening to Stay on Top of Their Content Game." *Radarr*, 21 Feb. 2022, www.radarr.com/blog/how-netflix-uses-social-listening/#:~:text=Builds%20a%20great%20customer%20relationship.
9. Chaffey, Dave. "Global Social Media Research Summary 2021." *Smart Insights*, 22 Aug. 2022, www.smartinsights.com/social-media-marketing/social-media-strategy/new-global-social-media-research/.
10. Chen, Jenn. "The Most Important Social Media Metrics to Track." *Sprout Social*, 26 Mar. 2021, sproutsocial.com/insights/social-media-metrics/.
11. "Digital 2022 Report Finds Social Media Users Now Equivalent to 58 Percent of the World's Total Population." *Www.businesswire.com*, 26 Jan. 2022, www.businesswire.com/news/home/20220126005361/en/Digital-2022-Report-Finds-Social-Media-Users-Now-Equivalent-to-58-Percent-of-the-World%E2%80%99s-Total-Population.
12. Dollarhide, Maya. "Social Media: Definition, Effects, and List of Top Apps." *Investopedia*, 31 Aug. 2021, www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-media.asp.
13. Gogolan, Diana. "Netflix's Social Media Strategy | Socialinsider." *Socialinsider Blog: Social Media Marketing Insights and Industry Tips*, 11 Mar. 2021, www.socialinsider.io/blog/netflix-social-media-strategy/.
14. Hayes, Adam. "What Is Social Media Marketing?" *Investopedia*, 29 July 2021, www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-media-marketing-smm.asp.
15. Jain, Parul, et al. "Magazines and Social Media Platforms: Strategies for Enhancing User Engagement and Implications for Publishers." *Journal of Magazine Media*, vol. 17, no. 2, 2017, 10.1353/jmm.2017.0018. Accessed 21 Feb. 2021.
16. Kaplan, Andreas M., and Michael Haenlein. "Users of the World, Unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media." *Business Horizons*, vol. 53, no. 1, Jan. 2010, pp. 59–68.
17. Kariuki, Patrick. "How and When Did Netflix Start? A Brief History of the Company." *MUO*, 22 Oct. 2021, www.makeuseof.com/how-when-netflix-start-brief-company-history/.
18. Mahoney, Megan. "Impact of Social Media in Today's Business World." *Single Grain*, Single Grain, 2 May 2011, www.singlegrain.com/blog-posts/impact-of-social-media-in-todays-business-world/.
19. McFadden, Christopher. "The Fascinating History of Netflix." *Interestingengineering.com*, 4 July 2020, interestingengineering.com/culture/the-fascinating-history-of-netflix.
20. Ngwainmbi, Emmanuel K. *Dismantling Cultural Borders through Social Media and Digital Communications : How Networked Communities Compromise Identity*. Cham, Springer International Publishing AG, 2022.
21. Omar, Mohamed Ali. "IMPACT of SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING on BUSINESS GROWTH in MOGADISHU-SOMALIAt." *Ummah Printing Center*, 1 Jan. 2019, www.academia.edu/39754115/IMPACT_OF_SOCIAL_MEDIA_MARKETING_ON_BUSINESS_GROWTH_IN_MOGADISHU_SOMALIAt.
22. Ortiz-Ospina, Esteban. "The Rise of Social Media." *Our World in Data*, University of Oxford, 18 Sept. 2019, ourworldindata.org/rise-of-social-media.

23. ---. "The Rise of Social Media." Our World in Data, University of Oxford, 18 Sept. 2019, ourworldindata.org/rise-of-social-media.
24. Parker, Brianna. "Netflix SWOT Analysis 2019 | SWOT Analysis of Netflix | Business Strategy Hub." Business Strategy Hub, 20 Mar. 2019, bstrategyhub.com/swot-analysis-of-netflix-2019-netflix-swot-analysis/
25. Pudvelis, Sara. "Matter Survey Reveals Consumers Find Influencers More Helpful and Trustworthy than Brands during the Pandemic." *Www.businesswire.com*, 26 May 2020, www.businesswire.com/news/home/20200526005058/en/Matter-Survey-Reveals-Consumers-Find-Influencers-More-Helpful-and-Trustworthy-than-Brands-During-the-Pandemic.
26. Ramakrishnan, Veena. "How Netflix's Social Media Strategy Dominates the Online Streaming Industry - Unmetric Social Media Analytics Blog." *Unmetric Social Media Analytics Blog*, 20 June 2019, blog.unmetric.com/netflix-social-media-strategy.
27. Rao, R. "Research Proposal Impact of Social Media - These Sites Range from Facebook to Instagram, Twitter." *StuDocu*, 2019, www.studocu.com/row/document/university-of-okara/financial-management/research-proposal-impact-of-social-media/7530348.
28. Rapp, Adam, et al. "Understanding Social Media Effects across Seller, Retailer, and Consumer Interactions." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 41, no. 5, 27 Jan. 2013, pp. 547–566, link.springer.com/article/10.1007/S11747-013-0326-9, 10.1007/s11747-013-0326-9.
29. Rodriguez, Ashley. "How Netflix Is Changing the Global Entertainment Industry." *Business Insider*, 24 Dec. 2021, www.businessinsider.com/how-netflix-is-changing-the-entertainment-industry-2021-8.
30. Sakshi. "Social Media: The Future of Marketing." *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, vol. 1, no. 1, 31 July 2017, 10.15520/ijcrr/2017/8/07/268.
31. Shaheem, S. "Research Proposal - Social Media Marketing - Effects of Social Media Marketing on Start up - StuDocu." *StuDocu*, 2020 www.studocu.com/row/document/limkokwing-university-of-creative-technology/introduction-to-international-business/research-proposal-social-media-marketing/10215092
32. Shastri, Aditya. Full Marketing Strategy of Netflix - Updated in 2022 | IIIDE. iide.co/presentations/marketing-strategy-of-netflix/
33. "Social Media Marketing [Critical Essay]: It's Pros and Cons | Total Assignment Help." *Www.totalassignment.com*, www.totalassignment.com/free-sample/pros-and-cons-of-social-media-marketing-critical-essay. Accessed 7 Dec. 2022.
34. Sutherland, Karen. "Importance of Social Media Marketing during COVID-19." *Www.palgrave.com*, 2020, www.palgrave.com/gp/blogs/business-economics-finance-management/importance-of-social-media-marketing-during-covid-19/18025270.
35. Team, T. L. "How Netflix Is Changing the TV Industry." *Investopedia*, 2022, www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/060815/how-netflix-changing-tv-industry.asp#:~:text=1%20By%20creating%20compelling%20original.
36. Tú, M. "Marketing Research - the Key for Netflix's Success." *En.hocmarketing.org*, 2022, en.hocmarketing.org/case-study/marketing-research-the-key-for-netflixs-success
37. Weller, Joe. "Here's How the Marketing Process Works | Smartsheet." *Smartsheet*, 16 Jan. 2019, www.smartsheet.com/strategic-marketing-processes-and-planning.
38. Wikipedia Contributors. "Influencer Marketing." *Wikipedia, Wikimedia Foundation*, 27 Mar. 2019, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Influencer_marketing.
39. Qualman, E. (2019). *Socialnomics: How Social Media Transforms the Way We Live and Do Business*. Wiley.
40. Mangold, W. G., & Faulds, D. J. (2009). Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix. *Business Horizons*, 52(4), 357-365.

41. Ryan, D., & Jones, C. (2019). *Understanding Digital Marketing: Marketing Strategies for Engaging the Digital Generation*. Kogan Page.
42. Evans, D., & McKee, J. (2014). *Social Media Marketing: The Next Generation of Business Engagement*. Wiley.
43. Weinberg, T., & Pehlivan, E. (2019). *Social Media Marketing*. Routledge.
44. Tuten, T. L., & Solomon, M. R. (2017). *Social Media Marketing*. SAGE Publications.
45. Barker, M., Barker, D. I., Bormann, N., & Neher, K. (2019). *Social Media Marketing: A Strategic Approach*. Cengage Learning.
46. Constantinides, E. (2014). Foundations of Social Media Marketing. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 148, 40-57.
47. De Vries, L., Gensler, S., & Leeflang, P. S. (2012). Popularity of brand posts on brand fan pages: An investigation of the effects of social media marketing. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26(2), 83-91.
48. Kietzmann, J. H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I. P., & Silvestre, B. S. (2011). Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media. *Business Horizons*, 54(3), 241-251.
49. Qualman, E. (2019). *Socialnomics: How Social Media Transforms the Way We Live and Do Business*. Wiley.
50. Mangold, W. G., & Faulds, D. J. (2009). Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix. *Business Horizons*, 52(4), 357-365.
51. Ryan, D., & Jones, C. (2019). *Understanding Digital Marketing: Marketing Strategies for Engaging the Digital Generation*. Kogan Page.
52. Evans, D., & McKee, J. (2014). *Social Media Marketing: The Next Generation of Business Engagement*. Wiley.
53. Weinberg, T., & Pehlivan, E. (2019). *Social Media Marketing*. Routledge.
54. Tuten, T. L., & Solomon, M. R. (2017). *Social Media Marketing*. SAGE Publications.
55. Barker, M., Barker, D. I., Bormann, N., & Neher, K. (2019). *Social Media Marketing: A Strategic Approach*. Cengage Learning.
56. Constantinides, E. (2014). Foundations of Social Media Marketing. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 148, 40-57.
57. De Vries, L., Gensler, S., & Leeflang, P. S. (2012). Popularity of brand posts on brand fan pages: An investigation of the effects of social media marketing. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26(2), 83-91.
58. Kietzmann, J. H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I. P., & Silvestre, B. S. (2011). Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media. *Business Horizons*, 54(3), 241-251

Ms Mokgabo Katlego Loeto

Email: mokgabokloeto@gmail.com